

ETHICAL STANDARDS AND JUDICIAL INDEPENDENCE: ENSURING INTEGRITY IN THE LEGAL PROFESSION

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Introduction

In the realm of law, the integrity and independence of the judiciary form the cornerstone of democratic governance and the rule of law. Ethical standards are not merely guidelines; they are fundamental principles that ensure judges and lawyers uphold the highest levels of professionalism, impartiality, and accountability. This article explores the vital role of ethical standards in the legal profession, focusing on their development, implementation, and impact on maintaining public trust in the judicial system.

From the historical evolution of legal ethics to contemporary international principles, the need for clear and enforceable ethical codes has never been more apparent. The Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct, among other significant documents, provide a comprehensive framework for judicial behavior, emphasizing the necessity of independence, impartiality, and integrity. By adhering to these principles, judges and lawyers can navigate the complexities of their roles while fostering an environment of fairness and justice.

This article delves into the mechanisms that support ethical conduct within the judiciary, including codes of ethics, judicial councils, and ethics commissions. It also examines the critical importance of ongoing education and training in ethics for legal professionals. By understanding and implementing these standards, the legal profession can enhance its credibility and ensure the effective administration of justice, thereby reinforcing the rule of law and democratic principles in society.

1. The Importance of Ethics in the Development of the Profession

At different stages of history, standards of ethics have varied significantly depending on the socio-economic environment and historical experiences. Ethics constitute a set of rules, norms of behavior, and standards adopted by society, which vary according to the specific characteristics inherent in each profession. The ethical standards set for doctors are distinctly different from those for judges or lawyers. While the obligation to act in good faith is common across all professions, ethical standards differ, reflecting the diversity of professions and the specific details and characteristics of each activity.

Undoubtedly, the development of professions is accompanied by the evolution of ethical standards. Conversely, the existence and relevance of ethical standards contribute to the development of professions.

The aim of ethics, which professionals face at the turn of each century, is the ability to establish rules that influence behavior.

Just as law develops in response to existing challenges, ethical standards have evolved and continue to evolve in accordance with historical context and current challenges. The legal profession is no exception. The development of legal professions has been accompanied by the evolution of ethical rules.

The history of legal ethics and its developmental stages are largely known and are associated with the evolution of law, spanning decades. Until the early twentieth century, there was no comprehensive code of ethics to regulate lawyers' behavior. Professional ethics were based either on innate views of ethical professional conduct or derived from other areas of law relevant to lawyers.

In 1887, the first code of ethics was created in the United States, specifically in Alabama. This code was based on an 1869 essay by George Sherwood and formed the foundation of several state codes of ethics. George Sherwood's antique book, an essay on professional ethics published in 1869, was based on lectures given at the University of Pennsylvania Law School in 1854.³⁹

The first ethics laws for American lawyers were passed by the American Bar Association (ABA) in 1908, perceived as a disciplinary code regulating lawyers' behavior. For the next fifty years, during a brief pause in the application of these rules, more emphasis was placed on the "gentlemanly" practice of law rather than on normative disciplinary standards. In 1964, under the direction of President Louis F. Powell, the ABA initiated a revision of existing laws, resulting in the creation of the Model Code of Professional Responsibility by 1969. This more detailed document contained nine "laws" accompanied by "ethical considerations." However, the code itself was met with criticism, mainly for the lack of clarity in its norms and the impracticality of certain issues.

In 1983, these rules were adopted as ethical standards in about thirty-five states, while others retained different versions of the Model Code. The ABA was not the only organization attempting to draft a comprehensive code; ethical standards in the legal profession at global and regional levels have developed significantly over the past 25 years, driven by the evolution of the profession and new challenges.

Unlike lawyers, the fundamental principle of judicial ethics—namely judicial independence—was first

³⁹ Sherwood was a judge of the District Court of Pennsylvania and later became Chief Justice of the Supreme Court of Pennsylvania. In his essay, Sherwood focused on important issues such as the behavior of a lawyer in the courtroom, emphasizing that a lawyer should not engage in behavior

aimed at disrupting the tribunal. Source [Accessed 21.02.2024]. See also Jones, W. B., "The First Legal Code of Ethics Adopted in the United States," *American Bar Association Journal*, 1922, 8(2), 111-113. Source [Accessed 21.02.2024].

mentioned in Article 10 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.⁴⁰ This article states, "In determining the rights and obligations or in determining the merits of any criminal charges submitted, everyone has the right to a fair and public trial of their case by an independent and impartial court." This principle was further developed in Article 14 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights⁴¹, adopted in 1966.

This principle, along with other important standards that should guide judicial conduct, was significantly expanded by the act adopted by the Seventh United Nations Congress—the "Basic Principles on Judicial Independence."⁴² These principles, adopted by the United Nations Congress in 1985, stated, among other things, that "the independence of the judiciary must be ensured by the state and protected by the constitution or law of the country. It is the duty of all governmental and other institutions to respect the independence of the judiciary."⁴³

At the regional European level, several key instruments of judicial ethics have been established. The European Association of Judges adopted the Charter of Judges in Europe in Wiesbaden, Germany, on 20 March 1993. In 1994, the Council of Europe Committee of Ministers adopted a recommendation on the independence, effectiveness, and role of judges, followed by the European Charter on the Statute of Judges adopted by the Council of Europe in Strasbourg in 1998.

Among the numerous standards and codes of conduct established by the network of legal professions or international organizations, special importance should be given to the Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct and the Magna Carta of Judges.

In April 2000, under the auspices of the United Nations, a group of presidents and supreme court justices from around the world gathered in Vienna to address the lack of public confidence in the judiciary. This meeting laid the foundation for the development of the Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct, an inspiring document that has led many states to adopt national codes of ethics. The basic principles presented in these standards have influenced the development of codes of conduct in many countries. The Bangalore Principles, in turn, address fundamental issues of fair trial and judicial integrity.

Judicial independence and impartiality are fundamental guarantees of a fair trial, forming the foundation of democracy and the rule of law.⁴⁴ The standards set by the Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct strengthen the legal system and, consequently, the rule of law. In a state governed by the rule of law, society has the right to demand the formation of general principles that align with the notion of a fair trial.

The profession of a lawyer, within any self-regulatory or legal framework, is based on respect for human rights, the protection of the rights of the parties, and the execution of justice. The existence of ethical standards is a crucial foundation for achieving these goals. The rules of professional conduct impose certain restrictions on lawyers, framing their behavior and indicating the expected conduct in conditions of fair competition.

The obligations imposed on judges, prosecutors, and lawyers are established to ensure their independence, impartiality, and effectiveness in serving the public. Public trust and respect for the legal profession are guarantees of the effectiveness of justice. The behavior of judges, prosecutors, and lawyers, both in the exercise of their functions and in their private lives, is essential for maintaining public confidence in the justice system. Therefore, representatives of the legal profession should be guided by proper standards of professional behavior. Ethical principles are not intended to establish directly enforceable standards of behavior but rather to offer guidance on overcoming difficulties faced in their professional and personal lives.

Learning a profession begins precisely from the student level. Teaching ethics is important not only for adhering to relevant standards in professional activities but also for the development of the profession itself. The education of lawyers and their preparation for the profession is not limited to obtaining theoretical knowledge. The primary goal of law school teaching is to teach students to think "like a lawyer." Rapid progress is achieved when students correctly understand legal processes, assess facts accurately, use proper legal language, and substantiate their positions with sound arguments. Law schools aim to develop skill-based abilities, emphasizing and consolidating the skills and ethical standards that are not only desirable but mandatory and necessary for a lawyer to possess.

The teaching modules of traditional law schools are often lacking in two main areas: client interaction experience and ethical substance. While the first may not necessarily be related to teaching methods, understanding ethical standards is a precondition for developing the legal profession and recognizing its importance. Professional ethics—teaching rules of professional conduct—is sometimes associated with "teaching professionalism," specifying appropriate rules of conduct, or simply encouraging politeness in some schools. Regardless of the approach, it is crucial to start understanding the importance of ethics from the doctrinal classroom. This will not only contribute to forming students into professional lawyers but also develop the legal profession in line with ethical standards.

⁴⁰ Universal Declaration of Human Rights, United Nations General Assembly, December 10, 1948.

⁴¹ "All persons are equal before courts and tribunals. Each person has the right, when considering each criminal charge brought against them, or when determining their rights and obligations in any civil process, to have their case fairly and publicly heard by a competent, independent, and impartial court established by law."

⁴² The act was passed by the Seventh United Nations Congress on the Prevention of Crime and the Treatment of Offenders in 1985 (August 26-September 6) and came into force

through General Assembly resolutions of November 29, 1985, 40/32, and December 13, 1985, 40/146.

⁴³ "Basic Principles on Judicial Independence," United Nations, Article 1.

⁴⁴ Article 6 of the European Convention on the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms establishes that "everyone has the right to a fair and public hearing within a reasonable time by an independent and impartial court established by law."

The impact of ethical standards on the profession is significant. Ethics plays a crucial role in the development of law and legal practice. As previously mentioned, the legal profession is built on the principles of law, justice, and the rule of law. Ethical standards and behavior towards the legal system are vital for maintaining public trust. Unethical behavior can weaken confidence in justice, making ethical standards essential for defining acceptable behavior boundaries.

The reputation of the legal profession is closely tied to society's perception of the administration of justice. If lawyers fail to follow and promote the principles of the rule of law and justice, access to justice will be hindered. Therefore, lawyers, as defenders of the rule of law and individual rights, bear significant responsibility to society. Low public confidence in the legal profession often translates to low confidence in the justice system itself.

The rule of law is integral to the legal profession. Since all individuals have the right to adequate protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms, regardless of their economic, social, cultural, civil, or political affiliation, effective access to legal services provided by an independent legal profession is required to protect these rights.

Professional ethics is key to ensuring an independent, competent, efficient, and accountable legal profession. Ethics, through the conduct of lawyers, can implement the principles of fairness, integrity, and public trust in justice. Making ethical standards a reality hinges on the ability to enforce them. Lawyers, as guardians of the law, carry enormous responsibility through the development of ethical rules, educating society about ethics, and providing effective disciplinary actions regarding ethics.

Ethical standards form the basis for the legal profession to be accountable for their actions. Accountability helps maintain the credibility of the legal system. In summary, ethics serves as a fundamental framework for the legal profession, guiding the behavior of lawyers and promoting public confidence in the legal system.

2. International Principles of Professional Ethics

Lawyers around the world are specialized professionals who prioritize their clients' interests above their own and strive to uphold respect for the rule of law. They balance legal actions in the interests of their clients with respect for the court and a legitimate aspiration to maintain a reasonable standard of living.⁴⁵ In this process, the rules of ethics play a crucial role. They act as important guidelines in the daily application of the law, ensuring appropriate behavior.

Improper ethical standards undermine the profession itself and, ultimately, justice. To ensure a high standard of practice and the independence of the profession, ethical standards must be developed by the profession's representatives. These principles of ethics

should be derived from domestic legislation and must comply with international and regional standards. Considered international sources of ethical behavior include:

- Contract norms
- Universal documents developed by the UN
- European standards developed by the Council of Europe and the European Union
- Universal and European standards established by professional and institutional bodies
- Decisions of international courts

Judges, prosecutors, lawyers, police officers, notaries, and teachers each have their own rules of ethics, though certain ethical standards are common across these professions. These include respect for and protection of the rule of law, human rights, respect for the parties, the obligation to protect professional secrets/privacy, fairness, and mutual respect. This chapter will review the above-mentioned and other main international standards in relation to each of these professions.

3. International Standards of Ethics for Judges

The main function of judges is to develop the law through judicial decisions. Judges are responsible for being moral compasses and exemplars of competence, professionalism, and impartiality for the societies they serve. Given the importance of their work, it is crucial to regulate judicial conduct to prevent judges from abusing their professional powers and thereby undermining trust in the judiciary and the rule of law. Consequently, judicial ethics have often been the subject of intense debate in both domestic and international forums.

Several tools can be employed to promote and implement judicial ethics:

- **Code of Ethics:** Formulates ethical principles.
- **Judicial Councils:** Promote ethical principles.
- **Ethics Commissions:** Provide advisory functions to help judges resolve ethical dilemmas.

Over the past decades, numerous documents have been adopted regarding the independence of judges. Initially, international acts focused solely on judicial independence, but standards of ethical behavior began to form in parallel. As a result, principles related to the ethical behavior of judges are now reflected in various reports and recommendations. These ethical standards are discussed in significant international and national documents that establish standards of judicial conduct.⁴⁶

In addition to relevant agencies and instruments promoting proper judicial conduct, numerous ethical standards have been set by various actors. Among these, the United Nations has developed various rules and documents on judicial conduct. In 1985, the General Assembly of the United Nations adopted the Basic Principles on the Independence of the Judiciary. These principles are part of customary international law and

⁴⁵ International Bar Association's International Principles on Conduct for the Legal Profession, International Bar Association, May 28, 2011, p. 5. Source [Accessed 15.02.24].

⁴⁶[https://www.coe.int/t/dghl/cooperation/lisbonnetwork/The mis/Ethics/Paper1_en.asp#:~:text=In%20order%20to%20have%20public's,of%20the%20societies%20they%20serve.>](https://www.coe.int/t/dghl/cooperation/lisbonnetwork/The%20mis/Ethics/Paper1_en.asp#:~:text=In%20order%20to%20have%20public's,of%20the%20societies%20they%20serve.>) [15.02.24]

are directed at the executive branch to promote and ensure the independence of the judiciary.

Ethical standards for judges are critical in maintaining public trust and the integrity of the legal system. Proper judicial conduct ensures that judges remain impartial, competent, and professional, reinforcing the rule of law and democratic principles in society.

The main principles reiterate those enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, emphasizing equality before the law, the presumption of innocence, and the right to a hearing by a competent, independent, and impartial tribunal. The twenty basic principles primarily address:

- **Independence of the Judiciary** (1-7)
- **Impartiality** (2)
- **Freedom from Inappropriate and Unreasonable Interference** (4)
- **Legal Provision of Procedures** (5)
- **Fair Conduct of Legal Proceedings** (6)
- **Freedom of Expression and Association of Judges** (8-9)
- **Qualification, Selection, and Training** (10)
- **Position and Status of Judges** (11-14)
- **Discipline, Suspension, and Dismissal of Judges** (17-20)

The most important document of judicial ethics is the Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct, adopted by the United Nations. These principles encompass independence, impartiality, integrity, propriety, equality, competence, and diligence. The document's final part states, "National courts should take reasonable steps to introduce mechanisms for implementing these principles, in case these mechanisms do not already exist in the relevant legal systems."

The Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct have received widespread recognition among those interested in ensuring high standards of justice. This document is designed to be universally applicable to judges. The values it reflects are essential for public confidence in the justice system.

Five years after adopting these principles, a group of judges working on judicial ethics developed detailed commentaries. These commentaries explain each value comprehensively and constitute the most extensive document on judicial ethics.

The Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct and their commentaries establish that judicial independence is not a privilege but a responsibility. The principle of separation of powers implies independence from other government branches and freedom from internal court influence. It is crucial that judges make decisions free from any influence.

To summarize the key points of the Bangalore Principles:

- **Independence:** Judges must be free from any external and internal influences.

- **Impartiality:** Judges must act without bias or favoritism.

- **Integrity:** Judges must maintain high moral standards in both professional and personal conduct.

- **Propriety:** Judges must exhibit appropriate behavior that upholds the dignity of their office.

- **Equality:** Judges must ensure that all persons are treated equally before the law.

- **Competence and Diligence:** Judges must possess the necessary skills and commitment to perform their duties effectively.

These principles serve as a guide for judges to uphold the highest standards of judicial conduct, thereby fostering public trust and maintaining the integrity of the judicial system.⁴⁷

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⁴⁷ The Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct were adopted by a group of judges, including fifteen Supreme Court chairmen, in The Hague, November 25-26, 2002. Source, p. 7.

⁴⁸ <https://www.supremecourt.ge/files/upload-file/pdf/aq-tebi15.pdf> p. 7

⁴⁹ "The lack of guarantees for the independence of judges within the judicial body, depending on the hierarchy, can lead the court to a dubious decision" - Parlov-Tkalčić v. Croatia, [2010] ECHR 86; also: Agrokompleks v. Ukraine, [2012] ECHR 137.

branches of government and freedom from internal court influence. It is crucial that judges make decisions free from any influence.⁵⁰

The principle of absolute prohibition of *ex parte* communication must be strictly observed by judges to strengthen their independence and impartiality. The guarantor of trust in the judiciary is an impartial judicial system. "Objectivity of the judge is a necessary condition for the proper performance of their duties. It manifests itself not only in the content of the decisions delivered but also in all procedural actions that accompany the adoption of these decisions."⁵¹

Bangalore's second value links impartiality to the exercise of judicial powers without bias, while the United Nations Basic Principles on the Independence of the Judiciary assert that the judiciary should decide cases freely, impartially, and without lawful direct or indirect influence.⁵²

The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights also focuses on the independence and impartiality of judges. Article 14 states that a judge's attitude towards the case and the parties involved should imply freedom from any influence.⁵³ Additionally, judges must always protect the prestige of the court and not allow their office to be used for personal interests.

In summary, maintaining judicial impartiality and independence is essential for upholding public trust in the judicial system. Judges must avoid *ex parte* communications and ensure their decisions and actions are free from bias and influence. This commitment to ethical conduct and impartiality reinforces the integrity of the judiciary and the rule of law.⁵⁴

Protecting the prestige and authority of the court requires judges to abstain from inappropriate behavior.⁵⁵ In its 21st opinion on the prevention of corruption among judges, the European Council of Judges recommends ethical conduct, ethical consultation, and training on ethics to strengthen the integrity of the court. It emphasizes the personal responsibility of judges for their behavior and the judicial system as a whole.⁵⁶

The French collection of ethical obligations of the court rightly notes that independent governance is also a state of mind. It includes knowledge and behaviors

that must be taught and evolve throughout a judge's career.⁵⁷

The establishment of ethical principles in codes of ethics has become the best practice to protect this principle. The code of ethics, as a living tool, helps judges successfully fulfill their duties in everyday life. It is a set of self-limiting rules, the observance of which is crucial for judges. In this process, it is especially important for the public to feel that judicial behavior is law-compliant and ethical.

In summary, maintaining ethical conduct and upholding the integrity of the judiciary require continuous education and adherence to a robust code of ethics. This ensures that judges not only follow the law but also maintain public confidence in the judicial system through their ethical behavior and decision-making.

Conclusion

Ethical standards are the bedrock of the legal profession, ensuring that judges and lawyers maintain the integrity, impartiality, and independence essential for a fair and just legal system. Through historical development and international consensus, frameworks like the Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct have established comprehensive guidelines that reinforce these core values.

The consistent application of these ethical standards fosters public trust and confidence in the judiciary, which is crucial for the effective administration of justice and the preservation of the rule of law. As the legal profession evolves, the importance of ethics education and ongoing training becomes ever more significant. Judges and lawyers must be well-versed in these principles to navigate the challenges of their roles while upholding the highest standards of professionalism.

By adhering to robust ethical codes and promoting a culture of accountability and integrity, the legal profession can continue to serve as a pillar of democracy. The commitment to ethical behavior not only protects the prestige and authority of the judiciary but also ensures that the rights and freedoms of individuals are safeguarded, thereby strengthening the fabric of society as a whole.

⁵⁰ Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct and its commentaries, TB, 2015, p. 67, §24.

⁵¹ Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct and its commentaries, TB, 2015, p. 91.

⁵² Resolution on the Basic Principles of Judicial Independence, Seventh United Nations Congress on the Prevention of Crime and the Treatment of Offenders, Milan, 1985, paragraph 2.

⁵³ Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct and its commentaries, TB, 2015, p. 67, §24.

⁵⁴ Ethical Principles for Judges, Canadian Judicial Council, 2021, p. 18, §F. Source [Accessed 12.02.24]. Also, Ethical

Principles for Judges, Canadian Judicial Council, 2021, p. 43, §c 10. Source [Accessed 12.02.24].

⁵⁵ Good faith compels a judge to refrain not only from acting contrary to the law, but also from any tactless or dishonest conduct," the Soviet European Network of Justice ENCJ, 2009-2010 Report, p. 4, §2.1; also, Bangalore Principles of the Conduct of Judges and its commentaries, TB, p. 129, §4.1.

⁵⁶ CCJE (2018)3Rev, p. 7.

⁵⁷ The Values of the Judiciary, Compendium of the Judiciary's Ethical Obligations. Source, p. 19.